

DATA PROTECTION STRATEGIES WITH ORACLE 19C TDE

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ABSTRACT

In today's age safeguarding data privacy and security has become a priority, for organizations in various industries. The rise in cyber threats and strict regulations highlight the need for measures to secure data. The findings indicate that Oracle 19c TDE offers a seamless and effective solution for data encryption, balancing security and performance. TDE offers functionality that streamlines encryption methods. Transparent Data Encryption (TDE) plays a role in addressing these security concerns by encrypting database files at the storage level ensuring data protection while avoiding the need for changes at the application level. TDE also protects data stored on storage media (tapes, disks etc.) in-case of an incident that the storage media or data file is lost or stolen.

Keywords: Transparent Data Encryption, TDE, Oracle 19C, Data Security, Encryption, Key Management, Compliance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Oracle Database 19c, the latest Support Release enhances, has enhanced TDE capabilities, with advanced features compared to previous versions. The encryption solutions offered by TDE in Oracle 19c seamlessly integrate with database setups reducing performance impact. By encrypting data files, redo logs and backups TDE ensures the security of information even if storage is compromised.

This document explores the use of TDE, in Oracle 19c focusing on its architecture, key management and operational efficiency. We cover the supported encryption algorithms, the process of implementing TDE and the tools in Oracle 19c for managing encrypted databases. Additionally we will explore how TDE supports organizations in adhering to regulations such, as GDPR, HIPAA and PCI DSS.

Through an analysis our aim is to provide insights into TDE in Oracle 19c and emphasize its role in strengthening data security while maintaining system performance. The discussion also covers considerations for deployment. We offer suggestions on how organizations can utilize TDE to protect their data assets. An important aspect of Transparent Data Encryption (TDE) in Oracle 19c is its implementation and management processes that help organizations enhance their data security posture.

TDE functions in Oracle 19c allowing existing applications to leverage encryption without the need, for modifications. This seamless integration is advantageous as it reduces the complexity and costs associated with adding security features to systems.

2. Simplicity in Implementation

One of the defining characteristics of Transparent Data Encryption (TDE) in Oracle 19c is its ease of implementation and management, which significantly lowers the barrier for organizations aiming to enhance their data security posture. Oracle 19c TDE is designed to operate transparently to applications, meaning that existing applications can leverage the benefits of encryption without any modifications. This seamless integration is a critical advantage, as it reduces the complexity and cost associated with retrofitting security measures into existing systems.

Simplified Setup Process -

Setting up Transparent Data Encryption (TDE) in Oracle 19c is a straightforward process thanks, to Oracles documentation and user friendly tools. The steps to activate TDE include generating a [1]master encryption key in the Oracle Wallet configuring the database for TDE usage and choosing which tablespaces or specific columns to encrypt. Oracle offers commands and scripts to assist with these tasks making it easy for database administrators to implement TDE with hassle.

Key Management -

In Oracle 19c there are enhanced key management features for safeguarding data. [1]The master encryption key is securely stored in the Oracle Wallet, a protected software container. Administrators can conveniently handle the wallet using tools provided by Oracle, such as the Oracle Key Vault for key management. This approach streamlines rotation, backup procedures and recovery processes while ensuring efficiency and security in TDE administration.

Automated Encryption Operations -

Once activated TDE seamlessly operates by decrypting data when writing to or reading from storage media. This automated functionality eliminates the need, for interference thereby reducing workload and minimizing the risk of human errors. Moreover Oracle 19c TDE offers a range of encryption algorithms giving administrators the flexibility to choose the security level, for their specific requirements without making encryption overly complex. process.

Minimal Performance Impact -

There is impact on performance with Oracle 19c TDE as it is designed to optimize encryption operations. The encryption and decryption processes are highly efficient ensuring that database performance remains strong during workloads. Oracles optimization techniques, such as using hardware acceleration for encryption tasks guarantee that TDE can be implemented without causing significant system performance degradation.

Comprehensive Documentation and Support -

Extensive documentation and support resources are provided by Oracle for TDE in Oracle 19c including guides, best practices suggestions and troubleshooting tips. These resources are invaluable for administrators in facilitating a deployment and ongoing management of TDE. Additionally Oracles support services are accessible to help address any issues that may arise ensuring organizations can confidently implement and sustain TDE. To sum up, the user friendly nature of TDE in Oracle 19c promotes it as optimal choice, for organizations looking to bolster their data security measures. Oracle 19c Transparent Data Encryption (TDE) offers a user solution, for securing databases with its setup strong key management, automated processes, minimal performance impact and extensive support.

3. Software - Oracle Transparent Data Encryption (TDE) What is TDE?

TDE encrypts data stored in data files to prevent unauthorized access. Unlike traditional encryption methods that require application-level changes, TDE operates transparently to applications, ensuring minimal disruption.

Components of TDE

- Wallet: A secure storage for encryption keys.
- Master Encryption Key: The top-level key used to encrypt other keys.
- Tablespace Encryption: Encrypts all data within a tablespace.

Figure 1: TDE Tablespace Encryption

- Column Encryption: Encrypts specific columns within tables.

Figure 2: TDE Column Encryption Overview

TDE operates within Oracle’s database architecture, leveraging Oracle Wallets and Key Management Framework (KMF) for key storage and management [1].

Oracle Wallet

The Oracle Wallet is a secure container that stores TDE master encryption keys. It supports both software and hardware security module (HSM) implementations.

Key Management Framework (KMF)

Oracle 19c introduces centralized key management, enabling easier key rotation and enhanced security controls. KMF supports:

- Key Lifecycle Management: Creation, rotation, and deactivation of keys.
- Unified Key Management: Integration with Oracle’s Advanced Security options.

Encryption Algorithms

Oracle 19c offers support, for a variety of industry standard encryption techniques, [1] such as AES 128, AES 192 and AES 256.

Algorithm	Key Size	Parameter Name
Advanced Encryption Standard (AES)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 128 bits (default for tablespace encryption) • 192 bits (default for column encryption) • 256 bits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AES128 • AES192 • AES256
ARIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 128 bits • 192 bits • 256 bits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARIA128 • ARIA192 • ARIA256
GOST	256 bits	GOST256
SEED	128 bits	SEED128
Triple Encryption Standard (DES)	168 bits	3DES168

Figure 3: TDE Encryption Algorithms supported

4. DISCUSSIONS

In the absence of Transparent Data Encryption (TDE), organizations are exposed to risks concerning data security and compliance regulations. Here are the primary risks associated with not implementing TDE:

Data Breach Risks

- 1) **Unauthorized Access:** Without TDE, sensitive data stored in databases becomes vulnerable to access in case the physical storage medium is stolen or accessed by individuals. This vulnerability includes threats from staff, external hackers or compromised backups.
- 2) **Data Theft:** Unauthorized individuals can easily duplicate data if they gain access to the storage location where database files are kept. This is especially critical for information like personal data, financial records and intellectual property.

Regulatory Non-Compliance

- 1) **Legal Consequences:** Various regulations such, as GDPR, HIPAA and PCI DSS require sensitive data to be safeguarded through encryption. Failure to implement TDE can lead to compliance issues that may result in substantial fines, legal consequences and penalties.
- 2) **Loss of Trust and Reputation:** A data breach could really harm a company's reputation. Break down trust, with customers. If the organization doesn't follow data protection laws it can make things even worse by affecting customer relationships and market position.

Financial Impact

- 1) **Direct Financial Losses:** Dealing with a data breach can be costly involving things like investigations, legal fees and compensating affected individuals.
- 2) **Indirect Financial Losses:** Indirect financial impacts could include missed business opportunities, lower stock value and higher insurance costs due to data protection measures.

Operational Risks

- 1) **Business Continuity:** In the event of a data loss or breach, the lack of encryption will escalate the situation and recovery efforts will be complex, prolonging downtime and disrupting business operations.
- 2) **Data Integrity and Security:** Without Transparent Data Encryption (TDE) the risk of unauthorized changes to data increases risk by jeopardizing its integrity and security.

Competitive Disadvantage

Companies that don't safeguard their data well may lose their edge in the market. Customers now prioritize data security when choosing service providers; if they feel their information isn't safe enough with one company they might switch to a competitor with better security measures in practice.

5. RESULTS

Here is a step-by-step guide to install and configure Transparent Data Encryption (TDE) in Oracle 19c [2] [4], ensuring data security and compliance with industry regulations.

Prerequisites

- Oracle Database 19c: Ensure you have Oracle Database 19c installed and configured.
- Database Privileges: You need DBA privileges to configure TDE.
- Access to SQL*Plus or another SQL interface.

Configure TDE Settings

- create user sec admin identified by secadmin account unlock;
- GRANT CONNECT, RESOURCE, CREATE SESSION TO sec admin;
- grant sysdba to sec admin;
- grant ADMINISTER KEY MANAGEMENT to sec admin;

```
SQL> conn / as sysdba
Connected.
SQL> create user sec_admin identified by secadmin account unlock;

User created.

SQL> GRANT CONNECT, RESOURCE, CREATE SESSION TO sec_admin;

Grant succeeded.

SQL>
SQL> grant sysdba to sec_admin;

Grant succeeded.
```

Figure 4:

```
SQL> grant ADMINISTER KEY MANAGEMENT to sec_admin;

Grant succeeded.
```

Figure 5:

```
ALTER SYSTEM SET WALLET_ROOT = 'C:\app\oracle\admin\orcl\Wallet' SCOPE = SPFILE;
Shutdown immediate;
STARTUP;
ALTER SYSTEM SET TDE_CONFIGURATION='KEYSTORE_CONFIGURATION=FILE' SCOPE=BOTH;
Create directory C:\app\oracle\admin\orcl\Wallet\ORA_KEYSTORES
ADMINISTER KEY MANAGEMENT CREATE KEYSTORE 'C:\app\oracle\admin\orcl\Wallet\ORA_KEYSTORES' IDENTIFIED BY "secadmin";
```

Figure 6:

```
SQL> ALTER SYSTEM SET WALLET_ROOT = 'C:\app\oracle\admin\orcl\Wallet' SCOPE = SPFILE;

System altered.

SQL> shutdown immediate
Database closed.
Database dismounted.
ORACLE instance shut down.
SQL> startup
ORACLE instance started.

Total System Global Area 1.0234E+10 bytes
Fixed Size 12577984 bytes
Variable Size 1644107168 bytes
Database Buffers 8556380160 bytes
Redo Buffers 20975616 bytes
Database mounted.
Database opened.
SQL> show user
USER is 'SYS'
SQL> ALTER SYSTEM SET TDE_CONFIGURATION='KEYSTORE_CONFIGURATION=FILE' SCOPE=BOTH;

System altered.

SQL> ADMINISTER KEY MANAGEMENT CREATE KEYSTORE 'C:\app\oracle\admin\orcl\Wallet\ORA_KEYSTORES' IDENTIFIED BY "secadmin";

keystore altered.
```

Figure 7:

```
SQL> select STATUS, WRL_PARAMETER, WALLET_TYPE FROM V$ENCRYPTION_WALLET;

STATUS          WRL_PARAMETER          WALLET_TYPE
-----
NOT_AVAILABLE  C:\APP\ORACLE\ADMIN\ORCL\WALLET\tde\  UNKNOWN
```

Figure 8:

Create and Open a Keystore with Auto login enabled Create a Password-Protected Keystore where encryption keys will be stored.

```
SQL> ADMINISTER KEY MANAGEMENT CREATE AUTO_LOGIN KEYSTORE FROM KEYSTORE 'C:\app\oracle\admin\orcl\wallet\ORA_KEYSTORES' IDENTIFIED BY "secadmin";
keystore altered.

SQL> shutdown immediate;
Database closed.
Database dismounted.
ORACLE instance shut down.
SQL> startup
ORACLE instance started.

Total System Global Area 1.022ME+10 bytes
Fixed Size 12277004 bytes
Variable Size 1044267168 bytes
Database Buffers 8556339200 bytes
Redo Buffers 20773616 bytes
Database mounted.
Database opened.
```

Figure 9:

Create the directory

C:\app\oracle\admin\orcl\Wallet\tde

Figure 10:

Open the keystore to allow for key management operations.

```
SQL> administer key management set keystore open identified by secadmin;
keystore altered.

SQL> select STATUS, WRL_PARAMETER, WALLET_TYPE FROM V$ENCRYPTION_WALLET;

STATUS          WRL_PARAMETER          WALLET_TYPE
-----
OPEN_NO_MASTER_KEY  C:\APP\ORACLE\ADMIN\ORCL\WALLET\tde\  PASSWORD
```

Figure 11:

Set the Master Encryption Key Set the master encryption key [1] using below statement. This will change the status from OPEN NO MASTER KEY to OPEN

```
SQL> administer key management set key identified by secadmin with backup;
keystore altered.

SQL> select key_id from v$encryption_keys;

KEY_ID
-----
Aa+HXId9/k9Nv9dvgwtTq4AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA

SQL> select STATUS, WRL_PARAMETER, WALLET_TYPE FROM V$ENCRYPTION_WALLET;

STATUS          WRL_PARAMETER          WALLET_TYPE
-----
OPEN            C:\APP\ORACLE\ADMIN\ORCL\WALLET\tde\  PASSWORD
```

Figure 12:

Encrypt Tablespaces The encrypted tablespace is created by using the CREATE TABLESPACE SQL statement with the option ENCRYPTION USING.[1]

Here is an Explanation:

If ENCRYPTION USING 'AES256' ENCRYPT is specified, then encryption algorithm and the key length for the encryption is defined. The ENCRYPT option encrypts the tablespace. The key lengths can be identified in the names of the algorithms. By default, encryption algorithm, AES128, is used if no encryption is specified. Below figures show SQL statements for different encryption algorithm. [1]

Below statement creates a tablespace that is encrypted using the AES256 algorithm.

```
CREATE TABLESPACE encrypt_ts DATAFILE 'C:\app\oracle\oradata\ORCL\encrypt_df.dbf'
SIZE 1M ENCRYPTION USING 'AES256' ENCRYPT;
```

```
SQL> CREATE TABLESPACE encrypt_ts DATAFILE 'C:\app\oracle\oradata\ORCL\encrypt_df.dbf' SIZE 1M ENCRYPTION USING 'AES256' ENCRYPT;
Tablespace created.
```

Figure 13:

Below statement creates a tablespace that is encrypted using the AES192 algorithm.

```
CREATE TABLESPACE securespace_1 DATAFILE
'C:\app\oracle\oradata\ORCL\secure01.dbf' SIZE 150M ENCRYPTION USING 'AES192'
ENCRYPT;
```

```
SQL> CREATE TABLESPACE securespace_1 DATAFILE 'C:\app\oracle\oradata\ORCL\secure01.dbf' SIZE 150M ENCRYPTION USING 'AES192' ENCRYPT;
Tablespace created.
```

Figure 14:

[1]Below statement creates a tablespace. Since there is no encryption algorithm is specified, the default algorithm AES128 is used. The key length is 128 bits.

```
CREATE TABLESPACE securespace_2 DATAFILE
'C:\app\oracle\oradata\ORCL\secure02.dbf' SIZE 150M ENCRYPTION ENCRYPT;
```

```
SQL> CREATE TABLESPACE securespace_2 DATAFILE 'C:\app\oracle\oradata\ORCL\secure02.dbf' SIZE 150M ENCRYPTION ENCRYPT;
Tablespace created.
```

Figure 15:

List of all encrypted tablespaces

```
select t.name, e.encryptedts, e.encryptionalg
from v$encrypted_tablespaces e join v$tablespace t on (e.ts# = t.ts#)
order by t.name;
```

```
SQL> select t.name, e.encryptedts, e.encryptionalg
2 from v$encrypted_tablespaces e join v$tablespace t on (e.ts# = t.ts#)
3 order by t.name;
```

NAME	ENC	ENCRYPT
ENCRYPT_TS	YES	AES256
SECURESPACE_1	YES	AES192
SECURESPACE_2	YES	AES128

Figure 16:

Creating a new table with Encrypted Column

```
CREATE TABLE hr.new_emp (
first_name VARCHAR2(128),
last_name VARCHAR2(128),
empID NUMBER,
salary NUMBER(6) ENCRYPT);
```

```
SQL> select owner, table_name, column_name, encryption_alg from DBA_ENCRYPTED_COLUMNS where table_name='NEW_EMP';
```

OWNER	TABLE_NAME	COLUMN_NAME	ENCRYPTION_ALG
HR	NEW_EMP	SALARY	AES 192 bits key

Figure 17:

Encrypting an Unencrypted Column in existing table

```
ALTER TABLE hr.emp_table MODIFY (ssn ENCRYPT);
```

```
SQL> alter table hr.emp_table modify (ssn encrypt no salt);
Table altered.

SQL> select owner,table_name,column_name, encryption_alg from DBA_ENCRYPTED_COLUMNS;
OWNER          TABLE_NAME    COLUMN_NAME    ENCRYPTION_ALG
-----
HR             EMP_TABLE      SSN            AES 192 bits key
```

Figure 18:

Transparent Data Encryption Related Views Used [2]

View	Description
ALL_ENCRYPTED_COLUMNS	Displays encryption information about encrypted columns in the tables accessible to the current user
DBA_ENCRYPTED_COLUMNS	Displays encryption information for <u>all of</u> the encrypted columns in the database
USER_ENCRYPTED_COLUMNS	Displays encryption information for encrypted table columns in the current user's schema
DBA_TABLESPACE_USAGE_METRICS	Describes tablespace usage metrics for all types of tablespaces, including permanent, temporary, and undo tablespaces
V\$DATABASE_KEY_INFO	Displays information about the default encryption key that is used for the current database. The default is AES128.
V\$ENCRYPTED_TABLESPACES	Displays information about the tablespaces that are encrypted
V\$ENCRYPTION_KEYS	When used with keys that have been rekeyed with the ADMINISTER KEY MANAGEMENT statement, displays information about the TDE master encryption keys. In a multitenant environment, when you query this view in a PDB, it displays information about keys that were created or activated for the current PDB. If you query this view in the root, it displays this information about keys for <u>all of</u> the PDBs.
V\$ENCRYPTION_WALLET	Displays information on the status of the keystore and the keystore location for TDE

Figure 19:

Additional Best Practices

- Regular Backups: Ensure regular backups of both the database and the keystore.
- Monitoring and Auditing: Periodically audit encryption settings and monitor for any unauthorized access.
- Updating Security Measures: Stay updated with Oracle's security patches and best practices.

6. COMMON ISSUES AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

When implementing Transparent Data Encryption (TDE) in Oracle 19c, several common issues can arise. Here are some of the most frequently en- countered problems [3] [4] along with their possible solutions:

Keystore Configuration Issues

Problem: Keystore not opening automatically

- Issue: After restarting the database, the keystore remains closed and must be manually opened.
- Solution: Ensure that the auto-login keystore is created correctly.

Master Key Issues

Problem: Master key not set properly

- Issue: Errors occur when trying to encrypt tablespaces or columns.
- Solution: Verify that the master key is set for both the Container Database (CDB) and each Pluggable Database (PDB).

Multiple master keys

Problem: Multiple master keys

- Issue: Confusion or errors related to the existence of multiple master keys.
- Solution: Regularly review the encryption keys. Periodically rotate keys and update encryption on sensitive data to use the latest master keys while securely archiving old keys. Regularly review and update security policies to align with compliance standards. Use Oracle Data Safe or similar tools to monitor and audit key management activities.

Wallet does not exist

Problem: Wallet does not exist

- Issue: Errors when trying to open the keystore.
- Solution: Check the wallet type parameter value is set. Create the directory in the path mentioned in the value if it does not exist.

```
SQL> administer key management set keystore open identified by secadmin;
administer key management set keystore open identified by secadmin
*
ERROR at line 1:
ORA-28367: wallet does not exist
```

Figure 20:

Problem: SYS owned object cannot be encrypted

- Issue: Errors when trying to encrypt objects in SYS.
- Solution: Make sure the object that needs to be encrypted is not owned by SYS.

```
SQL> ALTER TABLE emp_table MODIFY (ssn ENCRYPT);
ALTER TABLE emp_table MODIFY (ssn ENCRYPT)
*
ERROR at line 1:
ORA-28336: cannot encrypt SYS owned objects
```

Figure 21:

Problem: Column(s) cannot be both indexed and encrypted with salt.

- Issue: Column(s) cannot be both indexed and encrypted with salt.
- Solution: Encrypt without SALT. If indexing the encrypted column is critical for your application, you can encrypt the column without using salt. This way, the encrypted values remain consistent and can be indexed.

```
SQL> alter table hr.emp_table modify (ssn encrypt);
alter table hr.emp_table modify (ssn encrypt)
*
ERROR at line 1:
ORA-28338: Column(s) cannot be both indexed and encrypted with salt
```

Figure 22:

7. CONCLUSION

Utilizing Transparent Data Encryption (TDE), in Oracle 19c is a way to protect data at rest by encrypting database files and backup information. Organizations can utilize TDE to meet requirements and safeguard sensitive information, from access. The implementation of TDE includes steps like managing keystores generating keys and encrypting tablespaces or columns. It is vital to plan and execute each of these steps to prevent pitfalls such as keystore backup failures, performance issues and challenges with key rotation. While TDE offers advantages administrators need to be mindful of limitations like the incompatibility between salted encryption and indexing as well as the effective management of multiple master keys. To address these concerns recommended practices involve encrypting without salt when indexing is required maintaining an column for indexing purposes and using deterministic encryption where suitable. Regular backups, stringent security protocols and comprehensive testing in a staging environment are crucial, for ensuring the functioning and security of TDE. By following these guidelines organizations can effectively leverage TDE in Oracle 19c to strengthen their data security framework securely and consistently.

REFERENCES

- [1] Introduction to Transparent Data Encryption - 2023
- [2] Configuring Transparent Data Encryption - 2023
- [3] Transparent Data Encryption FAQ
- [4] Oracle SQL Language Reference: ALTER TABLE
- [5] Oracle® Database SQL Language Quick Reference
- [6] SQL Commands
- [7] Managing Keystores and TDE Master Encryption Keys in Isolated Mode
- [8] 2.2 Benefits of Using Transparent Data Encryption

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